

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF BALL AND ROLLER SLEWING BEARINGS IN THE MODERNIZATION OF AN EXCAVATOR SWING MECHANISM

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Abstract

This thesis considers the modernization of an excavator swing mechanism based on a comparative analysis of the operating characteristics of ball and roller slewing bearings. The study analyzes the assembly drawing of the swing mechanism, the structural parameters of the base, cover, and internal ring gear, as well as data on the material of the ring gear. As a result, it was substantiated that the use of a three-row cylindrical roller slewing bearing is the most optimal solution for an excavator swing mechanism operating under heavy load conditions.

Keywords: excavator, swing mechanism, modernization, ball bearing support, roller bearing support, ring gear, 40X steel.

Introduction

The reliable and efficient operation of excavators depends on the technical condition of their main mechanical units, particularly the swing mechanism. The swing mechanism ensures the rotation of the upper platform of the excavator and withstands axial, radial, and overturning moment loads that occur during operation. Therefore, the correct selection of the slewing bearing type used in this unit is of great importance.

In practice, ball and roller slewing bearings are used in such mechanisms. Although ball bearings have a simple structure, their load-carrying capacity may be limited in large-diameter mechanisms operating under high loads. Roller bearings, on the other hand, distribute the load over a wider contact area, which makes them more effective for heavy-duty operating conditions.[1]

Figure 1. General assembly drawing of the excavator swing mechanism.

Research Materials and Methods

In this study, the assembly drawing of the excavator swing mechanism, the drawings of the base, cover, and internal ring gear components, catalogue data of roller slewing bearings, and the results of spectral analysis of the ring gear material were examined.

During the analysis, the geometrical dimensions of the mechanism, mounting holes, supporting surfaces, ring gear parameters, and material composition were evaluated. In addition, the load-carrying characteristics of ball and roller slewing bearings were compared.[2]

Main Results

The analysis showed that the swing mechanism is a large-sized unit operating under high-load conditions. The maximum diameter of the base component is 2460 mm, and it contains 76 holes with a diameter of $\varnothing 26$ mm. The cover component has 78 holes with a diameter of $\varnothing 26$ mm, which increases the fastening stability of the mechanism.

The internal ring gear is the main component that transmits torque in the mechanism. Its main parameters are $m = 14$ and $z = 149$, indicating that the mechanism is designed for high-load operating conditions.[3]

Figure 2. Structural drawing of the base component of the swing mechanism.

According to the results of spectral analysis, the ring gear is made of **40Kh steel**. This material is characterized by high strength, wear resistance, and suitability for heat treatment. These properties are important for ensuring the long service life of the swing mechanism.

In ball slewing bearings, the load is transmitted through point contact. Under high-load conditions, this type of contact may lead to an increase in contact stresses. In roller bearings, however, the load is transmitted through line contact and distributed over a wider surface area. Therefore, roller bearings are considered more effective for heavily loaded excavator swing mechanisms.

Table 1. Comparative characteristics of ball and roller bearings

Indicator	Ball bearing support	Roller bearing support
Contact type	Point contact	Line contact
Load distribution	Limited	Stable
Resistance to heavy loads	Lower	High
Resistance to overturning moment	Lower	High
Suitability for large-diameter mechanisms	Limited	Suitable
Recommendation level	Relatively low	High

Discussion

The obtained results show that the selection of the slewing bearing type is one of the key factors in the modernization of an excavator swing mechanism. Although ball bearing supports are simple and compact in design, they are not sufficiently effective in large-diameter units operating under heavy loads.

Roller slewing bearings reduce contact stresses because they receive the load through line contact. In particular, in three-row cylindrical roller bearings, axial, radial, and overturning moment loads are received by separate rows. This makes it possible to increase the reliability and service life of the mechanism.

Conclusion

The analysis of the modernization of the excavator swing mechanism showed that the considered mechanism is a large-diameter unit designed to operate under high loads and transmit high torque. The structural parameters of the base, cover, and internal ring gear confirm that this mechanism was developed for heavy-duty operating conditions.

Although ball bearing supports are structurally simple, their capabilities are limited in heavily loaded excavator swing mechanisms. Roller bearing supports distribute the load over a wider contact area and ensure more stable operation of the mechanism.

Therefore, the use of a three-row cylindrical roller slewing bearing is recommended as the optimal design solution for the modernization of the excavator swing mechanism.

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